

ENHANCING PROFESSIONAL MOBILITY OF ENGINEERING STUDENTS

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Abstract

The students are taught in different ways of pedagogical methods according to their diverse needs and scientific interests. New innovative ways of teaching are foremost in the area of pedagogy at present time because the students are being interested in innovative technology. Besides, labor market is demanding highly qualified, knowledgeable, experienced engineers in the field of specialty. That's why, a great number of students are in need for professional mobility in the period of studies at the university. Moreover, the students need new methods of pedagogy in order to reach the expected goals. This paper highlights methodology and theory of pedagogy in teaching technical subjects and accomplishing the professional mobility simultaneously.

Key words: pedagogical methods, diverse needs, innovative technology, professional mobility.

Introduction

The pandemic has become a catalyst for the inevitable process of digitalization of communications, significantly changing the organization and technology of professional activity around the world. There has been radical change in labor market trends due to the digital transformation of the economy, changes in the employment rate, transition of professional groups to remote work format (A.A. Tarasyev, G.A. Agarkov, A.D.Sushchenko,

A.M.Tarasyev.2022:388-393). What's more, there is a gap and an imbalance between the needs of the labor market for highly qualified professionals and the training of young specialists by universities in areas of study where there is no shortage of human resources. Worth noting is the uncertainty of the constantly changing world, and interaction with it can, on the one hand, expand opportunities for unpacking innate inclinations, on the other – help actualize up-to-date knowledge. In these conditions, rapid development of new technologies is required. When applying for employment, university graduates are guided by the value orientations that they developed in the learning process, which determine their career trajectory necessary for the realization of existing knowledge, skills, for obtaining the desired income, professional and career growth. Furthermore, there is a need for pedagogical methodology in acquisition subject matter and doing professional mobility.

Literature Review

Nadia Lutsan, Olena Bulgakova, Olena Kuznetsova, Olena Babchuk, Svitlana Bykova (2021) conducted a research professional mobility for the teacher education and they claimed that the focus on the training of a specialist today is already insufficient; it is important to pay attention to the development of a personality capable of responding flexibly to constantly changing conditions, distinguished by entrepreneurship abilities, mobility, dynamism, constructiveness, and a developed sense of responsibility in professional activity. In this regard, in the modern higher pedagogical school, concepts are gaining increasing recognition in which priorities are given to the integral formation and development of the personality of the future teacher, the formation of the readiness to be mobile in professional activity by transferring from the state of performers to the state of actively acting subjects. To be a subject means to be internally ready for self-change in a rapidly changing world, to have the ability to rebuild life situations themselves, changing and developing at the same time as a person and as a professional. Studying the process of formation of the personality of a future teacher, researchers focus on the importance of such qualities as independence, responsibility, initiative in choosing learning goals and ways to achieve these goals (Avalos. B. 2011). Professional mobility of a future teacher is an integrated personal quality based on a high level of generalization of social and pedagogical knowledge and skills, which manifests itself not only in the readiness and ability to work creatively in the chosen profession, but also, if necessary, to choose a different type of professional activity within the framework of the specialties "human-human". Socio-pedagogical knowledge, skills and personal qualities formed in the process of studying psychological and pedagogical disciplines and during the period of pedagogical practice are universal for the professional activity of the "human-to-human" sphere, allowing a young specialist to successfully realize his potential not only in the teaching profession, but and be able to work in another specialty. Mobility is a necessary quality of any person, regardless of his professional activity, because the current sociocultural situation requires from a person not only the ability to adapt to this situation, but also the ability to effectively realize his personal potential. According to some experts, mobility is a person's individual response to the challenge of a changing world (Phelan.C.2006).

The main idea in recognition of professional mobility:

S.O. Boboyorov (2023:888-891) carried out a research on the issues of professional mobility and indicated that the main professional value is proper professional activity within the chosen specialty; Important professional values

(professional mobility; creative self-awareness in the profession; interpersonal communication; compliance with the professional image); Supporting professional values and emotional attitudes (critical attitude to one's professional knowledge; cognitive interest in theoretical aspects of professional activity; recognition of the high importance of the profession in society, etc.). The main goal of the pedagogical system for the development of social and professional mobility of a specialist is to create favorable conditions for the formation of competitive specialists with different levels of social and professional mobility, distinguished by professional skills, professional culture and reflection. Besides, high professional flexibility in the labor market. The process of developing socio-professional mobility of future specialists in the study of engineering sciences can be shown as a strategy implemented on the basis of the principles specific to this process. Among them, in addition to the generally recognized principles (scientific character; relevance of education to life; education and development; convenience) principles are also included:

1. Continuity of education, which implies the unity of all stages of the development process of professional mobility of future specialists in the study of agricultural sciences;

2. Consistency, which allows considering all the planned elements of the professional mobility development system as a whole with various internal connections between themselves and the external environment, reflects the completeness of the necessary forms in the educational activity of the university (Korjiva. E.M. 2005:197).

Conclusion

Professional mobility involves the engineering students in the area of agriculture to be more educated in the pedagogics because the methods and theory of pedagogy provides them with new ways of learning their subject matter during accomplishing professional mobility at working places. Besides, the engineering students need to be taught pedagogical methods which may able to improve their educational, social, professional skills. Pedagogical methods can make the engineering students to be competent in the area of agriculture.

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